

Fostering Well-Being with Machine Learning-Driven Indoor Plant Selection

Jeswin C Saji
PG Scholar
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
jeswincsaji@gmail.com

G.S Ajith
Asst.Professor
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
gsajith@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—In today's fast-paced urban environments, the importance of indoor plants in improving air quality, reducing stress, and enhancing well-being is increasingly recognized. This paper describes the creation of an indoor plant recommendation system based on machine learning to help people choose the best indoor plants based on their unique preferences and requirements. Our system evaluates user-provided preferences for things like stress relief, air purification, and aesthetics by using the Random Forest algorithm. It then offers tailored recommendations from a diverse collection of indoor plant species. The accuracy of our system is assessed, and the results demonstrate its potential to provide valuable insights and promote the integration of indoor greenery for healthier living. This paper discusses the methodology, results, and future possibilities for enhancing the user experience and extending the application of such systems in improving indoor environments and overall well-being.

Keywords—Random Forest Algorithm, Recommendation System, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Indoor plants have become a natural cure to bring balance back into our daily lives in an era of growing urbanization and corresponding disconnection from nature. These quiet, photosynthetic friends not only add vitality to our interior spaces but also have the ability to affect our mental and physical health. Beyond aesthetics, their presence is a live example of the symbiotic interaction between humans and the plant kingdom.

The numerous advantages of indoor plants are well known. They are organic air purifiers that may get rid of dangerous contaminants and fill indoor areas with clean, oxygen-rich air. These green companions also provide a respite from the pressures of modern life, which helps to noticeably lower anxiety and increase productivity. The promotion of mental health and the improvement of general quality of life serve as additional evidence of the peaceful coexistence of plant and human life.

However, choosing the ideal green companion suited to one's unique needs and preferences can be a difficult process given the wide variety of indoor plant species that are accessible. This is where technology fills the void, namely in the form of recommendation systems and machine learning. In this seminar paper, we set out to investigate the conception, creation, and use of a machine learning-based indoor plant recommendation system. Our system uses the Random Forest algorithm to give consumers the ability to choose indoor plants based on their own preferences, whether those preferences are related to stress relief, air

purification, aesthetic appeal, or a host of other considerations.

This study examines our recommendation system's methodology, including the procedures for collecting data,

preprocessing it, and training the model. It also assesses the accuracy of the system to look into how well it functions, giving a complete picture of its efficiency. We also take into account the numerous opportunities to expand the application of such systems to improve indoor environments and overall wellbeing, as well as to enhance the user experience.

We are reminded as we set out on this journey through the world of smart greenery that the fusion of technology and nature offers a creative answer to a very contemporary problem: how to transform our indoor spaces into not just livable but flourishing environments for the human spirit.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Indoor plants are becoming increasingly important in today's fast-paced urban environments for improving air quality, lowering stress levels, and boosting general well-being. The creation of machine learning-based indoor plant recommendation systems has gained prominence in order to meet the diverse preferences and requirements of individuals in choosing the most appropriate indoor plants. The foundational research in this field is examined in this literature review, which also lays the groundwork for the creation of a recommendation system for indoor plants.

Lohr and Pearson-Mims[4] conducted a study that showed how indoor plants can improve the comfort of indoor spaces overall and reduce stress. Their work highlights the therapeutic value of indoor vegetation in fostering more aesthetically pleasing and stress-free environments.

G. Fernandes et al.[1] presents the idea of deep learning for the identification and recommendation of indoor plants. It utilizes the strength of neural networks and sophisticated data processing techniques. It offers insightful information about how cutting-edge technologies, such as deep learning, can boost the efficiency of plant recommendation systems.

Liu[2] examines the use of the Random Forest algorithm in recommender systems for information personalization. It emphasizes the Random Forest algorithm's adaptability in personalization systems. It draws attention to the algorithm's potential for providing recommendations that are specifically catered to the needs and preferences of the user.

Lei and Ma[3], in their article provide a comprehensive review of recent advances in the relationship between indoor

greenery and human health. Their work highlights the positive impact of indoor greenery on human well-being, reinforcing the notion that indoor plants are not just aesthetic additions but also essential contributors to improved health and comfort.

Additionally, Mastin and Oliphant[5] discusses plant preferences and their tolerance to indoor conditions in the context of environmental science and development. This study may provide further insights into the selection and care of indoor plants.

III. MOTIVATION

The goal of creating indoor environments that are aesthetically pleasing, more personalized, and healthier is what inspired the creation of an indoor plant recommendation system. The system aims to use indoor plants' inherent ability to purify the air to make spaces cleaner and healthier. It is motivated by the realization that indoor air quality has a significant impact on occupants' well-being. Additionally, the motivation is fueled by the desire to offer tailored recommendations that are sensitive to users' individual requirements and preferences. This will help people get the most out of the plants in their indoor spaces, which will ultimately improve their mental and physical health. Another motivating factor is the aesthetic and psychological appeal of indoor plants, which not only improve the aesthetic appeal of indoor spaces but also have a positive impact on occupant well-being by lowering stress and increasing productivity. Furthermore, the system is in line with eco-friendly and sustainable trends, promoting indoor plant adoption as a sustainable and all-natural way to improve indoor air quality. The development of this system is further motivated by the desire to take advantage of machine learning advancements, as this fits in with the larger trend of utilizing technology to improve daily life. Last but not least, the wealth of research opportunities in this developing field motivates one to contribute by investigating novel methods and strategies to further improve the precision and individualization of indoor plant recommendations.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This includes gathering data, preparing it, choosing a machine learning model, training it, and designing the user interface.

A. Data Collection

A carefully curated dataset and user preferences gathered through an easy-to-use web interface are both used by the system to acquire comprehensive data. This dataset includes user preferences for different aspects of indoor plants, such as aesthetics, stress reduction, humidity increase, mental health, productivity, aroma benefits, sleep improvement and air purification.

B. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing involves cleaning and preparing the user preferences data for analysis. This includes handling missing values, data normalization, and encoding categorical variables. The data is then transformed into a format suitable for machine learning analysis.

C. Machine Learning Model Selection

The core of the recommendation system is a machine learning model. The Random Forest algorithm is chosen for its ability to handle both classification and regression tasks. It is trained on a dataset that includes a wide variety of indoor plant species, their characteristics, and their alignment with user preferences.

D. Training and Evaluation

The machine learning model is trained on a labeled dataset that contains information about indoor plants and their attributes. The training phase employs optimization techniques and algorithms to ensure that the model accurately captures the relationships between attributes and plant species, enhancing its recommendation capabilities. The model's accuracy is measured, and it's tested with a new dataset to provide personalized plant recommendations based on user preferences.

E. Recommendation Generation

When a user provides their preferences, the recommendation engine processes this input through the trained Random Forest model. The model generates a list of recommended indoor plant species based on the user's specific preferences and needs.

F. User Interface

The front-end user interface is designed to be user-friendly and visually appealing. Users can interact with the system by inputting their preferences and receiving personalized recommendations. The interface also allows users to explore detailed information about recommended plants, including care instructions and benefits.

G. Future Works

The system is designed with scalability in mind. As more data becomes available and user preferences evolve, the machine learning model can be retrained to improve recommendation accuracy. Future enhancements may include integration with smart home systems and real-time environmental data to further personalize recommendations.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

For building a reliable machine learning model for the successful indoor plant recommendation, we follow the following steps:

A. Import Libraries

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
import joblib
```

a) pandas(pd):

Description: Pandas is a popular Python library used for data manipulation and analysis. It provides data structures and functions for working with structured data, including dataframes. Pandas is used for reading and manipulating the dataset stored in 'plantsample.csv'

b) sklearn.model_selection

Description: This module provides tools for splitting the dataset into training and testing sets. In your code, `train_test_split` is used to split your dataset into a training set and a testing set, which is essential for training and evaluating machine learning models

c) `sklearn.ensemble`

Description: The `ensemble` module contains various ensemble machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest.

d) `sklearn.metrics`

Description: The `metrics` module in scikit-learn provides various metrics and tools for evaluating the performance of machine learning models.

e) `joblib`

Description: Joblib is a library for lightweight pipelining in Python. It is often used for efficiently saving and loading large data structures, including machine learning models.

B. Load Dataset

This section focuses on loading the dataset. It's the initial step in working with the dataset and making it accessible for further analysis and model training.

```
# Load your dataset
df = pd.read_csv('plantsample.csv')
```

C. Define Features and Target

It specifies the features and target variable. This process helps the machine learning model understand which attributes are relevant for predicting the target variable.

```
# Define your features (X) and target (y)
X = df[['Air Purification', 'Humidity Increase',
        'Stress Reduction', 'Mental Health',
        'Productivity', 'Sleep Improvement',
        'Aromatherapy', 'Aesthetic Pleasure']]
y = df['Plant Name']
```

D. Split the Dataset

The dataset is split into two parts: a training set and a testing set. This division is crucial for training the machine learning model on one portion of the data and evaluating its performance on the other.

```
# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

E. Create Random Forest Classifier

Random Forest is chosen for its ability to handle classification tasks effectively. This process involves creating a machine learning model known as a Random Forest classifier.

```
# Create a Random Forest classifier
rf_classifier = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=42)
```

F. Train the Model

The machine learning model is trained using the training set, which involves optimizing model parameters and algorithms. This training process ensures that the model captures the relationships between the features and the target variable accurately.

```
# Train the Random Forest classifier on the training data
rf_classifier.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

G. Make Predictions

With a trained model, predictions can be made on the testing set to evaluate its performance. The model generates predictions for the target variable based on the provided features.

```
# Make predictions on the test data
y_pred = rf_classifier.predict(X_test)
```

H. Results

Fig.1 Web interface where users select their preferences

Fig.2 Web interface that shows the recommended plants

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we described the creation of a machine learning-based recommendation system for indoor plants. This system's objective is to help users choose indoor plants that are appropriate for their preferences and requirements, including stress relief, humidity control, air purification, and more. The Random Forest algorithm is used by the system to generate customized plant recommendations. The proposed system leverages cutting-edge technology to enhance the indoor environment, offering tailored plant suggestions that promote well-being and improve indoor air quality.

We began by gathering and preparing a comprehensive dataset containing a diverse range of indoor plant species and their associated characteristics and benefits. This crucial dataset was compiled from various sources and curated to include details on factors like air purification, aesthetics,

humidity control, and more for each plant variety. Once collected, the dataset underwent preprocessing - steps like handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and normalizing the data - to transform it into a format optimal for machine learning model training.

The system is intended to be practical and easy to use. Through a web interface, users can enter their preferences, and the system generates recommendations in real time. The trained model, which considers user input and the data in the dataset, produces these recommendations. Based on the preferences provided by the user, the model showed good accuracy in predicting the best indoor plant varieties.

In conclusion, the indoor plant recommendation system presented in this paper represents an original and useful approach for people looking to improve the quality of their indoor environments through the addition of indoor plants. Through the utilization of machine learning and data-driven insights, users are empowered to make informed decisions regarding the plants that best suit their individual needs and preferences. This method makes living more pleasurable and sustainable by promoting an environment of improved well-being in addition to healthier indoor environments.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Fernandes, G., et al. (2020). "Indoor plant recognition and recommendation system using deep learning." *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 174(6).
- [2] Liu, T. (2022). "Random Forest Algorithm in Information Personalization Recommender System."
- [3] Lei, L., & Ma, J. (2019). "Indoor greenery and human health: Recent advances." *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1206.
- [4] Lohr, R. A., & Pearson-Mims, C. H. (1996). "The impact of indoor plants on human comfort." *Agricultural and Biological Engineering Department, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*.
- [5] Mastin, J., & Oliphant, V. (2015). "Plant preference and tolerance to indoor conditions." *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*, 6(2), 146.